

Envisioning the Role of Generative AI for Evidence-Based Software Engineering

Online Appendix

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I. EMPIRICAL VALIDATION

This Appendix presents how we empirically validate our framework’s proof of concept using established guidelines [1], [2]. We will cross-validate GAI outputs with human experts to assess their effectiveness and reliability in EBSE. *Research Identification and Search Strategy Development*. To assess the efficiency of GAI models for research topic identification and search strategy development, we can employ models such as OpenAI’s GPT-4, Google’s PaLM, and Meta’s LLaMA in comparison with human experts. Given a specific topic, mostly a replication study of an already published review can act as the basis for search string construction by human experts and the GAI models by comparing their search results against a dataset composed of search queries and their relevant studies compiled by a human.

Executing the Search and Mitigating Publication Bias. Literature searches are performed in academic databases based on such developed search strings. Using a curated dataset of previous studies, whose biases are known, based on searches using machine learning review techniques, it is possible to gauge whether GAI models identify a more diverse set of literature than traditional methods. We can test GAI models’ performance in mitigating publication bias by comparing the number of unique studies and the balance of study outcomes retrieved with different models identified and human experts.

Search Documentation and Compliance with Guidelines To what extent do GAI models document the search process using protocols such as PRISMA guidelines? Prompting the models to document the search strategy according to PRISMA standards will allow us to compare their output in terms of correctness, completeness, and conformity to reporting guidelines with documentation produced by human reviewers.

Study Selection and Quality Assessment. Human reviewers and GAI models can independently screen the studies based on one unified dataset of studies with predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inter-rater agreement metrics such as Cohen’s κ can be used to measure the consistency between the human selections and GAI models. Metrics like Kendall’s τ are helpful in measuring agreement in quality ratings between humans and GAI models.

Data Extraction and Synthesis. Using studies where data elements are pre-defined supports comparing the accuracy and completeness of data abstraction completed by GAI models and human reviewers. The GAI models’ performance is as-

essed by abstracting findings, sample sizes, methodologies, and outcomes requested of the GAI models. Regarding data synthesis, human reviewers and GAI models independently interpret and summarize findings across multiple studies. This enables measuring precision and qualitative data synthesis by GAI testing whether it outperforms or performs similarly to humans. Recent works from Esposito et al. [3], [4] already provide some evidence about the different performances of Open AI models in the extraction of key information from specific descriptions of scenarios and their diverse performance based on the use of RAG and task-specific fine-tuning.

REFERENCES

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